

**A STUDY ON THE DIFFERENCES IN TEACHING SKILLS OF PUPIL TEACHERS
& THE REQUIREMENT OF THE SCHOOLS**

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Abstract-

The present study has tried to explore the differences in teaching skills of pupil teachers being developed in teacher training institutions and the requirement of existing schools. The study has also tried to explore the academic skill of pupil teachers and the requirement of existing school of Govt. and private schools. The study has also tried to explore the administrative & co curricular skill of pupil teachers and the requirement of existing school of Govt. and private schools. The result reveled significant different in teaching skill of pupil teacher being developed in teacher training institutions & the requirement of existing Govt. & private schools.

Key Words- *Teaching Skills, Academic Skill, Administrative Skill, Co- Curricular Skill, Pupil Teacher, Existing Skill.*

Introduction—

The place of teacher can never be overestimated. The job of the teacher is to keep a balance between his duties to serve the sovereign, the state, and the society. Control and guide the action of the sovereign, the state and the society. The education commission 1966 says, 'off all different factors which includes the quality of education and its contribution to national development, the quality, competence and character of the teacher and undoubtedly the most significant.' For the fulfillment of this purpose and to train the teachers there are various types of teacher training program are introduced. The main purpose of these programs to trained the pupil teachers according to the norms and the requirement of the society.

Now in India there are various types of institution for organizing teacher education programmes at different levels like--

- Regional institute of education.
- Department of education in various universities.
- Colleges of education.
- NCERT
- DIET
- NCTE
- SCERT etc.

The status of the teachers reflects the socio culture ethics of society it is said that no people can raise the level of its teachers. There are lots of differences between teaching education and the requirement of the schools. The existing training program does not provide adequate opportunities to the student teachers to develop competency to face the various types of situation in their real teaching life because the organizer of teacher training programs are not aware of the existing problems of the schools. Due to this gap between the schools and the training institutions growth of contact stagnates, methodology gets state and contact with academic discipline become weak.

Objectives Of The Study--

- To study the differences in academic skills being developed among pupil teachers of teacher training institutions and the requirement of existing schools.
- To study the differences in administrative skills being developed among pupil teachers of teacher training institutions and the requirement of existing schools.
- To study the differences in co-curricular skills being developed among pupil teachers of teacher training institutions and the requirement of existing schools.
- To study the differences in teaching skills being developed among pupil teachers of teacher training institutions and the requirement of existing school.

Hypotheses-

- There may be no significant difference in academic skills among pupil teachers being developed by teachers training institute and the academic requirement of existing schools.

- There may be no significant difference in administrative skills among pupil teachers being developed by teachers training institute and the administrative requirement of existing schools.
- There may be no significant difference in co-curricular skills among pupil teachers being developed by teachers training institute and the co-curricular requirement of existing schools.
- There may be no significant difference in teaching skills among pupil teachers being developed by teachers training institute and the teaching requirement of existing schools.

Methodology—

Sample-

For the purpose of study the sample consists of 190 variable (pupil teachers of different institutes, teachers of govt. & private schools & teacher educators.)

Tools—

Self made questionnaire were used, consist 60 no of items with five rating scale.

Analysis & Discussion—

The analysis of present data indicates that the Academic skills of pupil teachers, govt. teachers and private teachers. It is clear that the Academic skills of pupil teachers are less than govt. & private teachers. So we can say that the pupil teachers are less skilled in comparison to govt. & private teachers, and there is significant difference between the Academic skills of pupil teachers being developed at teachers training institutions and required in existing schools.

Figure- 1: Academic Skills of Teachers

Figure-2: Administrative skills of Teachers

The analysis of obtained data shows that there is significant difference between the administrative skills of pupil teachers being developed among teacher training institutions and the requirement of existing schools. Figure 2 represents the Administrative skills of Pupil Teachers, Govt. Teachers and Private. Teachers. It is clear that the Administrative skills of Govt. teachers and Private. Teachers are more than the Pupil teachers. It shows that the Administrative skills of pupil teachers are not sufficient in actual conditions. It also represents the difference between the Administrative skills of pupil teachers being developed at teachers training institutions and requirement of existing schools.

Figure- 3: Co-curricular skills of Teachers

Figure 3 express the Co-curricular skills of pupil teachers and govt. & Private. Teachers. This figure shows much difference between pupil teachers and govt. teachers. The govt. & Private. teachers are more skilled in comparison to pupil teachers. So there is significant difference between Co-curricular skills of pupil teachers being developed that teacher training institutions and required in existing schools.

Figure-4: Teaching skills of Teachers

Figure-4 indicates that the Teaching skills of pupil teachers, govt. teachers and private teachers. It is clear that the Teaching skills of pupil teachers are less than govt. & private teachers. So we can say that the pupil teachers are less skilled in comparison to govt. &

private teachers, and there is significant difference between the teaching skills of pupil teachers being developed at teachers training institutions and required in existing schools.

Educational Implications

The most outstanding characteristic of any research is that it must contribute something new to the development of the idea concerned. So, the investigator has to find out educational implications of the study. Teacher education institutions are there to produce quality based teachers for the teacher. But sometime it comes to know that they are not fulfilling the requirement of the schools. The educational institutions must know the actual requirements of the school with the help of this they can produce a quality based teachers for the future. The goal of the educational institutions should be always within the reach, otherwise difference between student teacher and requirements of the school can be increased. The student teacher must know for the actual problems of the school. For reducing the problems the teacher education institution should organize meeting for student teacher and schools. Such meetings will help to reducing the difference between and requirement of pupil teachers and requirements of existing government and private schools. Educational institutions should design the curriculum based on actual problems of the school. Thus can be produced quality based teachers because they know the environment of the school.

Taking into consideration the major findings, it is found that there is too much difference between student teachers and actually required teachers by the schools. In this study it is also found that educational institutions are giving stress on practical knowledge, but in schools the theory part is in most consideration. These types of difference create problems for the student teachers when they came in the real world.

It is therefore suggested that student teachers must know that how to handle large classes including use of teaching learning equipments. The training colleges can take also effective steps towards guiding schools and their staff regarding improvement in their standard and working. The first requirement, therefore, is that the training colleges should take necessary steps to study the school conditions. It must be emphasized once again that no training colleges can really do effective work in isolation. They prepare teachers for the school and unless training assumes a functional and realistic bias it will loss all its significant. Schools and there needs must be put as the main hypothesis for such programmed, so that when the trainees bloom out as full fledged teachers they may not feel like standard in foreign hand.

Thus training colleges and school have, therefore to be nearer real classroom teaching should be allowed to examine critically the curriculum framework, syllabus, textbooks, etc. This study provides guideline to the teacher educators regarding Administrative skills, Academic skills, Co-curricular skills and Teaching skills. As per today's demands and needs, the study helps to formulate policies by the government. This study provides feedback to teacher training colleges.

Suggestions For The Removal Of The Differences

- ❖ The training curriculum should be flexible so that necessary adjustments and additions could be made without reference to the prescribing authority.
- ❖ To give a touch of reality to training, it is suggested that a seven day conference on "know the school problems" be arranged as the last item of the training course in all training institutions after the final examination.
- ❖ Old students should be put on the mailing list for all training colleges, publications and they continue as members of the college library.
- ❖ Training staff should be associated with school inspection and may be encourage holding demonstration lessons and faculty discussion during their visit. Members of the inspection able and headmaster are also encouraged to visit training colleges and share their ideas and experiences with the staff and the students.
- ❖ Item like multiple class teaching and how to handle large classes including use of new technologies should now form an important part of the educational methodology and organization. Training in improving material for science teaching is another innovation that could be embodied in the programmed.

Conclusion

At the end we can say that the teacher is the national builder and a good teacher prepared by the teacher educators in teacher training institutions. With the help of these institutions, the teachers trained and they learn various teaching skills. As we know that change is the law of nature so the structure of the education system is also changing. Change always demands improvement in old and something new in traditions. Nowadays the requirement of schools is different from the old school requirements. The new school system requires more capable teachers in various skills. So teachers should be according the needs of the present requirement that is prepared by training institutions. So with the help of this

research work the higher authorities of curriculum development, teacher training institutions and teacher educators can make effective to teacher training programme.

References

Aggarwal, Y.P. (1990). *Statistical Methods, Concept, Application and Computation*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers

Bansal, Arti. (2003). *Teacher Education, Principal, Theory and Practice* Meerut: Surya Publications

Bhai V.K. (2003). *Correlates of Total quality culture in teacher Education Institutions, fifth Survey of research in education*, New Delhi: NCERT

Biswas, Aggarwal (2001). *Encyclopedic Dictionary and Directory of Education* New Delhi. The Academic publishers India Vol-1

Buch, M.B. (1978-83). *Teacher's Education. Third Survey of Research in Education*

Dash, M (2004). *Education in India*. Agra: Ray Publications

Ganapathy, S. (1992). *Self Concept of student teachers and their attitude towards teaching profession*. M.phill (kuk)

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